

The Red Rectangle: a thin disk with big grains and gravel

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There is a very uniform class of post-AGB stars in binary systems with 85 members in the Galaxy. These sources consist of a F-G post-AGB primary and a MS secondary (left; adapted from Gallardo-Cava 2023, PhD Thesis). The system is surrounded by a circumbinary disk made of gas and dust from which a low velocity disk-wind bipolar flow escapes. The MS companion accretes material either from the inner (dust-free) regions of the disk or the primary, launching a fast but very tenuous ionised bipolar jet.

The best studied case of this kind of objects is the Red Rectangle (right; Cohen et al. 2004). The total central mass is $1.8 M_{\odot}$ and the orbital period is 317 d. We will adopt a distance of 710 pc. The system is O-rich but presents strong emission in PAHs, CI and CII. We mapped the source in ALMA Cycle 0, detecting the disk and the disk-wind. The former is in sub-Keplerian rotation while the latter escapes at low velocity with a small rotating component consistent with the wind being released from the disk. Here we present new ALMA Cycle 7 observations at 20 mas (14 AU) resolution of the innermost parts of the disk (Bujarrabal et al. 2023, Alcolea et al. 2023).

The band 7 (0.9 mm) observations presented here have been obtained in ALMA project 2019.1.00177.S, using two array configurations with baseline lengths from 14 m to 14.9 km. The observed frequency ranges are 330.350 – 332.658 and 343.563 – 346.032 GHz, with a spectral resolution of 0.21 – 0.85 km/s. In addition to the continuum, we have detected spectral line emission from ^{12}CO , ^{13}CO , H^{13}CN , H_2O , and SiO . Spatial resolution is 20 mas, equivalent to 14 UA at 710 pc.

The image of the continuum emission (left top), consists of a central compact component (CCC) plus the contribution of a thin disk seen almost edge-on: the dusty disk component (DDC). The total detected fluxes are 664 and 722 mJy at 331.7 and 344.5 GHz respectively. Apart from the compact central component (CCC), the strongest emission in the map comes from a region 200 mas wide in diameter (140 AU) and 25 mas in height width (18 AU). We obtain a total flux of 8.3 mJy and a size of 15 mas (10 AU) for the CCC.

To compute the physical parameters of the dust disk component (DDC) that dominates the continuum emission of the Red Rectangle a 0.9 mm, we have developed a simple model of radiative transfer for a dust grain nebula. We have adopted simple laws for grain absorption/emissivity (scattering is not important at these wavelengths): a constant emissivity for wavelengths smaller than 10 times the grain radius R_g , and an emissivity that decreases inversely proportional to the wavelength otherwise. We have also adopted a grain density of 2.5 gr/cm³, typical of O-rich dust material. We have included the contribution from a small central component to account for the emission from the CCC.

The best fitting of the data (left bottom) has been obtained for a characteristic grain radius R_g of 0.15 mm, comparable to the value of 0.2 mm previously inferred by (Jura et al. 1997). The temperature of the dust varies inversely to the square root of the distance to the centre, with a value of 550 K at $1.8 \cdot 10^{15}$ cm (120 AU), and an upper limit of 1200 K. We derive a total dust mass in the disk of 25 Earth masses. This is 100 times smaller than the molecular total mass of the disk (Gallardo-Cava et al. 2023).

Apart from large grains, our model also finds a strong settlement of solid material onto the equatorial plane of the disk: 80% of the disk's solid mass lies at distances from the equatorial plane smaller than $4 \cdot 10^{14}$ cm (~ 53 AU in width). The size of this dense disk is also relatively small, with a width-to-height ratio of about 10: disk radius of $4 \cdot 10^{15}$ cm (~ 530 AU in width). These sizes are significantly smaller (about 1/8) than the distribution shown by the molecular gas.

We have estimated the spectral indexes for both the DDC and the CCC by comparing our fluxes with those from the literature at cm- and sub-mm-waves (Jura et al. 1997, Bujarrabal et al. 2013, 2016). The results are shown in the figure to the right. For the CCC, the derived spectral index (SI) is 0.8, very close to the expected value of 0.6 for an isothermal ionised wind of constant mass loss (Pangia& Felli 1975). This component was previously associated to free-free emission by Jura et al. (1997). Our result confirms the nature of this emission which we conclude is due to the bipolar jet launched by the companion. Using the fluxes derived at 0.9 mm, and assuming that the size measured for this component is several times the "so-called" characteristic radius, we derive a temperature of 3600 – 10,000 K, and a mass loss rate of $0.8 - 1.7 \cdot 10^{-7} M_{\odot}/a$.

The SI measured for the DDC, 2.13, is very close to the value expected for an optically thick emission, or the emission of very big grains with flat emissivity up to 3 cm wavelength. Using our dust emissivity model, we have checked that even for grains 0.3 mm in diameter, a SI of about two requires unrealistic values of the total dust mass. On the contrary, our finding suggests that there must be a population of even larger sizes, up to 1 cm in diameter, responsible for the flat emissivity of this dust disk up to 3.6 cm. It is suggested that dusty disks orbiting around post-AGB stars may be sites for second-generation planet / planetesimal formation (Völschow et al. 2014; Scicluna et al. 2020; Kluska et al. 2022). The detection of gravel particles 1 cm in size represents a result of utmost importance in this field.

Regarding the spectral line results, due to the lower S/N ratio we only present results for 55 mas (40 AU) and 0.5 km/s resolutions. Both ^{12}CO and ^{13}CO J=3–2 are well detected but just from the disk and the innermost regions of the bipolar outflow; the outer parts are too faint and have been partially resolved out.

No gas depletion has been found in these equatorial parts, contrarily to what happens in disks orbiting around young stars, but note that here the dust temperatures are higher and this effect is not expected. The Keplerian kinematics of the disk is very nicely shown in the PV diagrams; on the left we show the results for ^{12}CO . Reconciling the observed velocities with the central mass requires the presence of a significant radial expansion velocity component in the rotating disk too. From the data we derive $V_{\text{rot}} = 8 (r/R_{\text{int}})^{-1/2}$ and $V_{\text{exp}} = 5 (r/R_{\text{int}})^{-1/2}$, with $R_{\text{int}} = 28$ AU. Also, there is no significant molecular gas emission for distances to the centre closer than R_{int} . The outer molecular radius reaches a value of 3000 AU. The opaque ^{12}CO emission displays a brightness temperature similar to that of the dust ≈ 300 K.

